

Endogenous generation of genomic diversity through reverse transcription and homologous recombination.

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Abstract

It is commonly believed that organisms diversify their genomes through point mutations, insertions, and deletions. Here, I propose a complementary mechanism: Diversity Generation by Reverse Transcriptase (DGbyRT), in which cellular or exogenous RNAs are reverse transcribed into cDNA and integrated into the genome via homology-directed recombination. This process enables the reuse of modular genetic information—derived from both coding and non-coding transcripts—focusing variation on functionally relevant regions and improving the efficiency of genomic exploration.

DGbyRT draws on mechanisms observed across life, including diversity-generating retroelements, retrotransposons, telomerase, and somatic hypermutation, and may involve endogenous RTs such as Pol- θ . I hypothesize that transcribed pseudogenes and duplicated sequences serve as reservoirs for recombinable modules. DGbyRT may also contribute to somatic-to-germline communication, with reverse-transcribed RNAs crossing the Weismann barrier to influence heritable change.

Inspired by synthetic biology tools such as the Autodime method [3], DGbyRT is presented as a regulated, context-sensitive diversification strategy. As RNA-based technologies advance, understanding natural reverse transcription mechanisms becomes increasingly relevant to both evolutionary biology and therapeutic innovation.

Introduction

Living organisms adapt to their environments through evolutionary changes in the genome. Because DNA sequences are long and complex, the genomic space they span is vast, with most random mutations resulting in deleterious or neutral effects [1]. This imposes the need for efficient strategies to explore genomic space. Traditionally, random point mutations, insertions, and deletions are seen as the primary drivers of genomic diversification.

Here, I propose a more efficient, information-rich mechanism: Diversity Generation by Reverse Transcriptase (DGbyRT). In this hypothesis, RNA molecules produced by the cell—regardless of their origin or function—can be reverse transcribed into cDNA by endogenous reverse transcriptases (RTs) and recombined into the genome at homologous loci. This process effectively “recycles” pre-existing, biologically meaningful sequence segments, combining them in new contexts to create functional variation while avoiding exploration of vast, unproductive genomic space.

DGbyRT can act both as a DNA repair mechanism and as a diversity generator by introducing slightly different DNA versions originating from other loci with high homology, or errors inherent in the reverse transcription process. Such homologous sequences—including paralogs, pseudogenes, and motif-rich RNAs—are more likely to yield functional outcomes than entirely random mutations.

Although reverse transcriptase was first discovered in retroviruses, homologous enzymes are ancient and widespread across all three domains of life [2]. In humans, endogenous RT activities include telomerase, which maintains chromosome ends by copying an RNA template, and DNA polymerase theta (Pol θ), which exhibits RT activity comparable to viral RTs and participates in RNA-templated DNA repair. These enzymes provide plausible molecular machinery for the DGbyRT mechanism proposed here.

A Synthetic Biology-Inspired Device: Autodime

In 2011, while exploring strategies to improve protein functionality through directed evolution, I developed and patented a method that I called Autodime (Autonomous Directed Mutagenesis) [3] to diversify specific genomic elements in vivo using a mechanism based on random oligonucleotide substitution (see Fig. 1).

In the Autodime, a plasmid carries a library of oligonucleotide sequences, each of which shares high sequence homology with a target gene or gene fragment. These oligonucleotides are transcribed into mRNAs independently. Within the same cell, a reverse transcriptase (RT)—specifically the Moloney Murine Leukemia Virus (MMLV) RT—is also expressed. This RT reverse-transcribes the transcribed mRNAs into complementary DNA (cDNA). During cell division, these cDNA fragments can undergo homologous recombination with the genome at their matching loci, thereby modifying the target DNA (recombineering [4]). Although the set of oligonucleotides is defined by the plasmid library, the specific oligonucleotide that undergoes recombination is selected stochastically, with probabilities biased by sequence homology and, to some extent, by random variations arising from imperfect reverse transcription.

The method to generate ssDNA in *E. coli* cells was previously reported by Chen et al. [5], building upon foundational work on intracellular ssDNA production and recombination mechanisms developed in C. Conrad lab [6]. More recently, similar approaches of Autodime have been refined by other groups [7], by employing HIV-derived RT to enhance recombination efficiency [8].

In an Autodime plasmid, multiple blocks of homologous sequences—each compatible with a genomic target site—are transcribed. These may encode structural variants of proteins, regulatory sequences, or binding motifs. Through combinatorial recombination of the resulting cDNAs, a population of cells acquires genomic diversity localized to specific genes or regions of interest. The only essential requirement is that the inserted blocks maintain sufficient sequence homology—particularly at their termini—with the genomic target site.

This raises a fundamental question: What if Autodime is not merely a synthetic biology tool, but instead mimics a naturally occurring cellular mechanism?

To distinguish the natural version from the engineered mechanism, I refer to this putative endogenous mechanism as DGbyRT—Diversity Generation by Reverse Transcriptase.

DGbyRT, in a sense, represents a more conservative mechanism than classical mutation. Any DNA sequence that is transcribed and does not harm the cell becomes available as part of a reservoir of alternative genetic elements. In this light, sequences that once encoded active genes remain beneficial by persisting in the genome; although no longer translated, they may retain functional potential in other genomic contexts. These homologous sequences—especially when stored in non-coding regions—can still be transcribed and recombined with active genes.

To assess the plausibility of DGbyRT, I will draw from theoretical arguments based on genetic algorithms and optimization in high-dimensional search spaces. I will then review known examples in which reverse transcriptase is used by cells to diversify DNA in both prokaryotic and eukaryotic systems. Finally, I will propose how DGbyRT may function generally in cells and explore the hypothesis that, unlike classical random mutation, DGbyRT can be regulated, introducing the possibility of a form of Lamarckian, environment-responsive evolution.

The Curse of Dimensionality and Genetic Algorithms

In the conventional neo-Darwinian view, gene mutations and their phenotypic consequences are considered independent events. Mutations are assumed to occur randomly, without feedback from phenotypic outcomes, resulting from the intrinsic inefficiencies of DNA-repair mechanisms. While exceptions like stress-induced mutagenesis exist [9], the dominant model treats mutation as unregulated and stochastic.

Organisms face a dual optimization problem: translating DNA into a foldable, functional protein—an NP-Hard computational task—and adapting it to dynamic environments. Navigating such a high-dimensional and rugged fitness landscape requires efficient search strategies, as the “curse of dimensionality” makes locating global optima computationally intractable.

In Genetic Algorithms, a schema is a pattern of characters sharing fixed positions [10], and populations evolve by conserving and recombining short, high-fitness schemata.

Analogously, genomes contain functional sub-gene elements—structural motifs or regulatory sequences—that share partial homology across loci. These sequence blocks can occur in both coding and non-coding regions.

Directed evolution experiments exploit the modularity of genomes by introducing diversity through block shuffling, followed by PCR assembly and selection, efficiently sampling sequence space near known functional configurations [11,12]. DGbyRT echoes this logic by introducing variation via reverse transcriptase-mediated recombination. Like the Autodime method, it allows modulation of mutation rates and confines changes to specific physiological states or genomic regions, including targeted recombination among a limited set of homologous sequences.

Evolvability

Kirschner et al. [13] define evolvability as an organism’s capacity to tolerate variation in its essential components—a trait critical not only for natural evolution but also for engineering adaptive biological systems [14]. A related concept, gene plasticity, described by Mayo et al. [15], refers to a gene’s potential to evolve novel but functional roles.

On the fitness landscape, evolvability enables exploration of wide, flat peaks that tolerate multiple genetic configurations, while plasticity refers to reaching alternative peaks not too distant from the current configuration.

These properties are not trivial. The “curse of dimensionality” means any single DNA sequence is an isolated point in a vast space of mostly non-viable or neutral solutions, making exploration inefficient without guidance mechanisms.

A conservative mechanism like DGbyRT, which recombines existing DNA blocks rather than relying on random mutations, can focus exploration on regions already near functional configurations. This increases the probability of remaining within viable genomic territory, enhancing fitness preservation.

Evolvability may be enhanced when the genome contains multiple homologous DNA blocks that can be recombined in new contexts. Such modularity does not guarantee viability, but it increases the likelihood that resulting variants retain biological relevance, as the sequences involved already have functional viability in other contexts. In this framework, the “evotype” concept of Castle et al. [14]—a set of nearby, minimally altered configurations that retain function—becomes relevant. DGbyRT, by favoring recombination among such blocks, may bias genomic exploration toward this accessible space, mitigating the risk of random deleterious mutations.

Sparsity of Viable Mutations

Empirical studies mapping the fitness landscape of proteins reveal that viable evolutionary paths are exceedingly sparse, underscoring the ruggedness and constraints of protein fitness spaces.

Weinreich et al. [16] examined the mutational space of the β -lactamase enzyme across five amino acid substitutions. While the final configuration achieved over 100,000-fold increased antibiotic resistance, most mutational trajectories passed through non-functional intermediates that failed to fold correctly or lost function entirely.

A more recent study by Starr et al. [17] used fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS) and deep sequencing to analyze the receptor-binding domain (RBD) of SARS-CoV-2. Assessing fitness along folding, ACE2 binding affinity, and antibody escape, they found most point mutations deleterious to folding and binding, with significant positional variability in mutation tolerance.

These findings highlight a key constraint in protein evolution: viable mutations are rare and typically confined to narrow mutational corridors. Mechanisms like DGbyRT, which can recombine functional modules instead of relying solely on single-site mutations, may therefore offer an evolutionary advantage by enabling safer traversal of these sparse fitness pathways.

RNA as a Template for Mutations

What types of RNA could serve as templates for DGbyRT? The reverse transcription process is constrained by the biochemistry of reverse transcriptase, which typically requires the presence of a tRNA primer and may be influenced by RNA secondary structures. Within these biochemical boundaries, potential RNA sources include both endogenous and exogenous RNA molecules.

Endogenous mRNA produced by actively expressed genes can be reverse transcribed and used for either genome repair or, less frequently, mutagenesis. This is due to the inherently higher error rate of reverse transcriptase compared to standard DNA polymerases.

A partially homologous cDNA can also insert longer stretches of novel sequences. Importantly, even RNA transcribed from non-coding or inactive genomic regions can serve as templates, thereby expanding the diversity potential.

Exogenous RNA, originating from other cells within the same organism or even from entirely different organisms, may also participate in DGbyRT. This introduces a channel for RNA-mediated genetic exchange, enabling intercellular and possibly interspecies transfer of genetic

information. When reverse transcribed and integrated through DGbyRT, such RNA could effectively mediate horizontal gene transfer by replacing orthologous sequences.

Several studies support the plausibility of this mechanism. In J. Probst et al. [18], they demonstrated that mRNA uptake by cells is an active, selective process. T. A. Shtam et al. [19] showed that exosomes can shuttle small RNA molecules between cells. K. Wang et al. [20] suggested that extracellular RNA from microbiota and diet may be present in human plasma.

Together, these findings offer biological plausibility to the idea that RNA from diverse origins can serve as input for genomic modification via reverse transcription and homology-driven recombination.

Regulatory Potential of Enzyme-Induced Mutation

A key feature of DGbyRT is its basis in enzymatic processes, which opens the possibility for active regulation. Unlike purely stochastic mutation mechanisms, the steps involved in reverse transcription and homology-directed recombination can, in principle, be modulated by cellular signals or environmental cues.

Figure 2 illustrates a conceptual synthetic biology framework in which the Autodime mechanism is placed under the control of an external regulatory signal. This model indicates how genome diversification via reverse transcription could be made conditional, activated only in response to specific triggers, such as stress, signaling molecules, or developmental stages.

Moreover, because DGbyRT operates through the modular recombination of homologous sequences, it enables identical or similar genetic elements to acquire new functions when integrated into different genomic contexts. This process, known as exaptation, facilitates the repurposing of existing sequences for novel roles, thereby driving functional innovation in genome evolution.

Diversity-Generating Retroelements

Is there any experimental evidence that supports the existence of DGbyRT or a similar natural mechanism in cells?

Indeed, a known process shares many features with DGbyRT: the Diversity-Generating Retroelement (DGR). Unlike typical retroelements that primarily amplify themselves within the genome, DGRs function to diversify specific protein-coding sequences. They operate through a targeted mutagenic process known as “mutagenic homing,” in which a donor template repeat (TR) transfers sequence information to a recipient variable region (VR). During reverse transcription, adenine residues in the TR are subject to systematic mutation, producing variation in the VR.

Although DGR differs from Autodime—particularly in that it does not use a block-based oligonucleotide library and relies instead on error-prone reverse transcription—it still demonstrates that reverse transcriptase-mediated sequence diversification is a natural, biologically functional process.

First discovered in a *Bordetella* bacteriophage [21] [22], DGR systems have since been identified across a wide range of life forms, including eukaryotes, prokaryotes, and viruses, underscoring the evolutionary significance and ubiquity of RT-based diversification.

RT-Mediated Somatic Hypermutation

Another biological mechanism resembling Autodime is somatic hypermutation in immunoglobulin genes [23]. Here, targeted diversification occurs in the V[D]J region, with the VH region providing a combinatorial library of gene segments. There is growing evidence that an RT-mediated reverse transcription step may contribute to the generation of these hypermutations [24].

The proposed model for diversification is deaminase-driven reverse transcription (DRT), which shares several features with the DGR mechanisms previously described. DRT refers to a process in which cytidine and adenosine deaminases (such as AID, APOBEC, and ADAR) introduce targeted mutations into RNA or DNA. These edited sequences are then reverse transcribed by error-prone reverse transcriptases like Pol η or Pol θ . This mechanism is thought to play a significant role in generating genetic diversity in the immune system and has been implicated in cancer, where APOBEC activity and endogenous reverse transcriptase contribute to mutational signatures and genomic instability.

Cellular Reverse Transcriptases: Pol- θ and LINE Elements

Reverse transcriptases (RTs) are not exclusive to retroviruses; they are widespread in both Metazoan and Plantae, often associated with endogenous retroelements and transposable elements [25]. In humans, a particularly notable example is DNA polymerase theta (Pol- θ), which exhibits reverse transcription activity comparable to that of viral RTs such as Moloney murine leukemia virus (M-MuLV) and avian myeloblastosis virus (AMV) [26]. Although initially characterized for its role in repairing DNA lesions, Pol- θ 's broader physiological functions remain largely unexplored, making it a strong candidate for endogenous reverse-transcription-based genome modification. Other polymerases, like Pol- η , also possess RT activity, but Pol- θ stands out for its unusually high efficiency. Additionally, Long Interspersed Elements (LINE-1), a class of mobile genetic elements abundant in mammalian genomes, encode their own RT, which may also contribute to DGbyRT by reverse transcribing cellular RNAs into cDNA that integrates into the genome [27].

Presence of RNA Template from Non-Coding DNA

The ENCODE project revealed that approximately three-quarters of the human genome is transcribed. However, only around 3% of this genome corresponds to expressed protein-coding genes (roughly 20,000), and an additional ~18,000 sequences code for pseudogenes. The function of the vast majority of the transcriptome remains unclear, though mounting evidence suggests it plays a role in gene regulation.

While multiple explanations exist for the pervasive transcription of non-coding regions, what is most relevant for the DGbyRT hypothesis is the extensive availability of transcribed sequences. Many of these transcripts originate from duplicated genes or pseudogenes and often exhibit significant homology with both coding sequences and regulatory elements.

Concerted Evolution

DGbyRT may also offer insight into the phenomenon of concerted evolution—the observation that paralogous genes within a species are often more similar to each other than to homologous genes in related species [28]. This intra-species homogeneity is usually attributed

to mechanisms like gene conversion or transposon-mediated homogenization. As an alternative or complementary explanation, DGbyRT suggests that RNA transcribed from one locus could be reverse transcribed and recombined into homologous loci, helping maintain or restore sequence similarity within multigene families.

RNA Migrating from Somatic to Gametic Cells

Evidence suggests that RNA produced in somatic tissues can traverse the Weismann barrier and reach germ cells, particularly epididymal spermatozoa [29]. Once there, such RNA may be reverse transcribed via LINE-1–encoded reverse transcriptase, forming cDNA that exists as extrachromosomal DNA or becomes integrated into the genome [30].

Since germline cells undergo mitotic and meiotic divisions involving homologous recombination, the integration of reverse-transcribed cDNA is mechanistically plausible. LINE-1 elements—endogenous retrotransposons active in germ cells—provide the necessary enzymatic machinery for such events.

Mourier [31] reviewed how retrotransposable elements embed transcriptional regulatory motifs, suggesting their influence on genome architecture and function. In metazoans, much evolutionary innovation arises from changes in gene regulation [32]. DGbyRT could contribute to this diversification by mobilizing regulatory RNA templates and reinserting them into new genomic contexts—especially during ontogenesis, when regulatory precision is essential.

The role of reverse transcriptase in genomic innovation is longstanding. McClintock [33] proposed that transposable elements act as genomic control elements responsive to stress. Subsequent studies have confirmed that retrotransposons and their RTs can restructure genome content and regulation (34, 35). Extending this view, the DGbyRT hypothesis posits that transcribed gene fragments or pseudogene-derived RNAs may serve as modular blocks for stochastic recombination, contributing to genome evolution in a structured, context-sensitive manner. This may explain both the widespread transcription of non-coding DNA [36] and the ubiquity of RT enzymes across life forms [31].

Cellular Fate and Localization of Reverse-Transcribed cDNA

If reverse transcription is a common and functional process in cells, an important question is where the resulting complementary DNA (cDNA) resides. Several possibilities exist. One is that cDNA may remain transiently in the cytoplasm, where it can await nuclear import for potential integration or be degraded if not utilized. However, growing evidence indicates that cDNAs can also localize to the nucleus, where they may integrate into the genome via homology-directed repair mechanisms or non-homologous end joining [37]. In fact, cells experiencing DNA damage often exhibit increased nuclear uptake of nucleic acids, potentially providing opportunities for cDNA integration [38].

Retrotransposon activity, such as that of LINE-1 elements, illustrates how reverse-transcribed cDNAs are directed into the genome using endogenous machinery [39]. Similarly, viral integration into host genomes typically proceeds through cDNA intermediates transported into the nucleus (Temin 1989). Thus, the cellular machinery for cDNA nuclear entry and integration is not only available but actively used in multiple biological contexts.

Zhang et al. [40] demonstrated that SARS-CoV-2—despite being an RNA virus lacking a native reverse transcriptase—can have its RNA reverse-transcribed and partially integrated into the genome of human cells in culture. This integration appears to be facilitated by flanking pairing sequences and recognition by the LINE-1 endonuclease. Notably, integration sites tend to be

biased toward exonic regions of the genome, consistent with a mechanism that diversifies actively coding genes rather than non-coding regions.

It remains unclear how frequently non-viral, endogenously produced cDNA from cellular RNA becomes fixed in the genome. However, several studies have detected extrachromosomal cDNA fragments in contexts such as viral infection and cancer [41]. It is also possible that many integration events go unnoticed due to their subtle effects or localization in non-coding regions. Nevertheless, the accumulation of such events over evolutionary time could contribute significantly to genome evolution.

Role of Reverse Transcriptase in Alzheimer's Disease

Recent research has implicated reverse transcriptase (RT) activity in the genomic instability associated with various pathologies, including cancer and neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's. In particular, mosaic recombination of the APP (Amyloid Precursor Protein) gene has been observed in neurons of Alzheimer's patients, suggesting the presence of somatic gene recombination processes potentially driven by endogenous RT activity [42].

In the context of DGbyRT, it is notable that APP gene cDNAs have been shown to generate thousands of distinct genomic variants derived from the cellular gene itself. These variants contain intra-exonic junctions (IEJs) and numerous single-nucleotide variants (SNVs), can undergo multiple retro-insertions into the genomes of post-mitotic neurons, and appear capable of being actively transcribed and translated to produce diverse bioactive products relevant to both normal physiology and disease states [42].

Several studies have also investigated the use of RT inhibitors—commonly employed in antiretroviral therapy—as a means to suppress the aberrant genomic alterations associated with Alzheimer's progression. These findings support the idea that RT activity, when dysregulated, may contribute to pathological genome remodeling.

Targeting Stress-Induced Diversification in Cancer Therapy

A key hypothesis of the DGbyRT framework is that reverse transcription and homologous recombination constitute a conserved cellular response to stress, not merely by-products of retroelements or immune processes. Under environmental or internal stress—such as oxidative damage, nutrient deprivation, or cytotoxic treatment—cells may activate pathways that temporarily boost their capacity for diversification. DGbyRT could serve as a last-resort mechanism, enabling somatic cells to explore alternative phenotypic solutions when conventional responses fail.

This process may be particularly active in cancer cells, which often face high levels of genotoxic and therapeutic stress. If tumors exploit DGbyRT-like mechanisms to enhance genetic or epigenetic heterogeneity, then inhibiting reverse transcription or homologous recombination could offer a novel therapeutic strategy—one that limits the emergence of treatment-resistant subclones and improves long-term outcomes.

Recent studies support the role of reverse transcriptase activity in therapy resistance and genomic instability. RT inhibitors have been shown to restrict LINE-1 retrotransposon mobilization, suppress pro-inflammatory signaling, and reduce drug-resistant variants in cancer cell populations [43, 44, 45]. Nucleoside RT inhibitors such as stavudine and lamivudine, in particular, block LINE-1 activity and downstream NF- κ B and interferon signaling, decreasing cellular plasticity under stress [44, 45].

These findings suggest that stress-induced reverse transcription and recombination are not aberrations of malignancy but may represent a general somatic diversification response. If so, DGbyRT itself could be targeted across multiple clinical contexts—from cancer to degenerative diseases—where maladaptive diversification plays a role.

Future research should aim to identify molecular markers of DGbyRT activity—such as chimeric transcripts, cDNA intermediates, or recombination scars—and assess their correlation with treatment outcomes. Patient stratification based on DGbyRT signatures could guide the strategic use of RT inhibitors, opening a novel direction in precision oncology.

How to Test the DGbyRT Hypothesis

A distinctive feature of the DGbyRT hypothesis is that it predicts not simply an overall increase in mutation rate, but a specific pattern of sequence diversification constrained by the repertoire of homologous sequences available within a single cell. Rather than introducing random point mutations or small indels uniformly, DGbyRT enables sequence changes that are compatible with existing homologous templates in the genome.

DGbyRT is expected to diversify specific genes by introducing variations that reflect the sequence homology already present in the cell. Actively transcribed genes may recombine with pseudogenes or duplicated regions sharing partial homology, leading to modular replacements or motif shuffling that preserve functional coherence. This mechanism can generate novel but viable variants while avoiding the highly deleterious consequences of purely random mutations.

Crucially, this recombination-based diversification is principally intracellular. It depends on the presence of homologous sequences within the same genome. Thus, if a gene has many duplicated or pseudogene copies within one individual's genome, DGbyRT can act on it efficiently, producing new allelic variants through internal recombination. By contrast, if homologous copies exist only across different individuals in a population (but not within their genomes), DGbyRT cannot act with the same efficiency. In these cases, classical mutational mechanisms like point substitutions—which occur independently in each individual—remain the main source of variation at the population level.

In addition, reverse transcriptases themselves may introduce characteristic patterns of copy errors during the generation of cDNA, distinct from those made by standard DNA replication enzymes. This means that even when recombination occurs between highly homologous regions, the errors introduced by reverse transcription could add a bias or signature to the resulting diversity. Genes with many transcribed, high-homology copies might therefore show, in a statistical sense, the imprint of RT-mediated recombination in their mutation spectrum. Experimental work on candidate endogenous RTs, such as Pol-theta, can test for these preferential error patterns by comparing mutation profiles generated during RNA-templated DNA synthesis.

Another experimental approach involves manipulating RT activity directly in cellular populations under selective pressure. For example, applying reverse transcriptase inhibitors to a population of rapidly reproducing cells—such as bacteria, yeast, or cancer cells—could test whether limiting RT activity reduces the population's adaptive potential under stress or selective challenge. Conversely, enhancing RT activity or expression in a controlled setting might increase the emergence of beneficial variants, accelerating adaptation. Comparing these

experimental conditions would help assess whether DGbyRT-like mechanisms genuinely contribute to evolvability by enabling more efficient exploration of adaptive solutions.

Together, these strategies—analyzing recombination patterns within genomes, profiling RT error signatures, and testing RT inhibition or enhancement in evolving populations—offer concrete, testable paths to evaluate the role of DGbyRT in shaping genomic diversity.

Conclusion

This hypothesis proposes a fundamentally distinct mechanism of genome diversification—Diversity Generation by Reverse Transcription (DGbyRT)—in which cellular or exogenous RNAs are reverse transcribed into cDNA and integrated into the genome via homology-directed recombination. Rather than relying solely on point mutations or random insertions and deletions, DGbyRT offers a more efficient and potentially targeted way to explore genomic space. It is inherently conservative, favoring the reuse of functional or formerly functional genetic modules already present within the transcriptome, especially pseudogenes and duplicated non-coding regions.

Notably, in multicellular organisms with differentiated tissues and slower generational turnover, classical point mutations may be too inefficient to generate adaptive diversity rapidly enough to keep pace with changing environments. In such contexts, a mechanism like DGbyRT could provide a crucial evolutionary advantage by enabling cells to leverage existing homologous sequences to produce meaningful, functionally relevant variation in fewer generations.

Inspired by synthetic biology systems like Autodime, DGbyRT combines reverse transcription and sequence homology to enable modular rewiring of genomic information. Evidence from bacterial diversity-generating retroelements (DGRs), retrotransposons, telomerase activity, immunoglobulin gene hypermutation, and the activity of cellular reverse transcriptases such as Pol- θ suggests that reverse transcription is already a widespread cellular mechanism that can be repurposed for controlled diversification.

If experimentally confirmed, DGbyRT would challenge the traditional neo-Darwinian model of random, independent mutations by introducing the possibility of regulated, modular mechanisms that preserve evolvability while maintaining genomic stability. This perspective has profound implications for our understanding of so-called “junk DNA,” reframing it as a reservoir of recombinogenic templates poised for adaptive reuse when needed.

The DGbyRT hypothesis suggests that life has evolved a fundamentally different strategy for exploring genomic space: one that reuses existing genetic information via RNA reverse transcription and homology-based recombination. Rather than relying solely on the slow, often inefficient accumulation of mutations, this mechanism would allow cells to draw from a vast reservoir of transcribed sequences—including pseudogenes, non-coding RNAs, and even exogenous RNAs—to generate meaningful variation in a targeted manner. In this way, DGbyRT also provides a potential explanation for the evolutionary maintenance of many transcribed pseudogenes and duplicated sequences that seem to lack clear cellular function.

A particularly intriguing aspect of DGbyRT is its potential to bridge somatic and germline compartments, suggesting a route for molecular communication across the Weismann barrier. This raises the possibility that reverse-transcribed RNA originating in somatic cells could influence germline genomes, potentially linking environmental experiences to heritable genomic changes.

DGbyRT is not proposed as a constant or uncontrolled source of mutation. Rather, it is envisioned as a conditionally activated mechanism, tightly regulated and infrequent in action, generating useful diversity without destabilizing the genome through excessive mutagenesis. This balance between innovation and stability is key to its evolutionary plausibility.

The implications are not merely theoretical. Understanding DGbyRT could inspire new therapeutic strategies—from targeted gene repair using synthetic RNA templates, to inhibiting maladaptive diversification in cancer by blocking endogenous reverse transcriptase activity. It also raises testable predictions about the relationship between gene copy number and mutation rates, the distribution of homologous motifs in genomes, and the presence of cDNA intermediates in cells.

Methodologically, this hypothesis exemplifies a synthetic biology–inspired approach to evolutionary theory. Originally conceived as a patented engineering solution (Autodime) for in vivo directed evolution, DGbyRT represents—if supported by evidence—an instance of Richard Feynman’s famous dictum: “What I cannot create, I do not understand.” By constructing an artificial system to generate diversity, it offers a concrete model that can suggest a naturally occurring phenomenon. This reflects an epistemological approach, where scientific understanding is achieved not only through observation but also through the capacity to design and recreate the underlying processes, reinforcing the role of building as a path to knowing.

Confirming or refuting the DGbyRT hypothesis will require interdisciplinary collaboration, combining evolutionary theory, molecular biology, synthetic biology, and computational modeling. If validated, it would enrich our understanding of evolution as not merely a random walk through genomic space, but as a dynamic, regulated exploration of modular, pre-existing solutions—a powerful strategy for life to balance innovation with stability.

Figure 1. Comparison of classical directed evolution and the Autodime method.

(A) In classical directed evolution, functional selection is followed by in vitro recombination and transformation of DNA extracted from selected variants.

(B) In the AutoDiMe method, diversification occurs in vivo through recombination of homologous reverse-transcribed sequences, eliminating the need for intermediate DNA extraction and in vitro recombination. External intervention is required only for the initial “bootstrap”; thereafter, the process can proceed autonomously, allowing the cell population to generate new variant libraries and evolve continuously. AutoDiMe—activated at each cycle, for example by a temperature shift—can be halted once the desired selection or screening criteria are met.

A)

B)

Figure 2. AutoDiMe-coupled synthetic receptor enabling phenotype-to-genotype feedback.

In this illustrative two-component signaling system AutoDiMe (Autonomous Directed Mutation Engine) is functionally coupled to a membrane-embedded histidine kinase and its cognate receptor. The receptor spans the bacterial envelope, exposing a periplasmic sensor domain composed of two modular arms encoded by a gene under selection. Ligand binding to the sensor domain activates the histidine kinase, leading to phosphorylation of the response regulator (RR) and transcriptional activation of a downstream genetic cassette. This cassette includes AutoDiMe components—reverse transcriptase (RT) and λ Red recombination machinery—placed under control of the RR-responsive promoter. In the absence of ligand binding, AutoDiMe is activated and iteratively reshuffles or replaces domains within the receptor gene by recombination from a domain library, generating variant sensor architectures. The process continues in a closed loop until a receptor variant capable of ligand binding emerges, at which point signaling is restored and AutoDiMe activity is downregulated. In this system, the phenotypic performance of a protein (ligand binding) directly biases the genetic modifications that generated it, establishing a directed phenotype-to-genotype feedback loop. This constitutes a synthetic, Lamarckian-like evolutionary process that departs from the classical molecular biology dogma by allowing protein function to influence the evolution of its own encoding DNA.

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